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IMPORTANCE OF SILVER CARP (*HYPOTHALMICHTHYS MOLITRIX*) FISH IN THE AQUACULTURE

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada do'ngpeshona baliqlarining biologik, ekologik xususiyatlari, tabiatdagi va inson hayotidagi ahamiyati, baliqchilik sohasida tutgan o'rni, yetishtirish, olib borilgan turli ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari, o'rganilish tarixi va ularning taxlili shuningdek, yurtimizda akvakultura sharoitida yetishtirish afzalliklari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: oq va chipor do'ngpeshona, fit ova zooplankton, biomeliator, bioekologik xususiyat.

Аннотация. В статье рассмотрены биологическая и экологическая характеристика тельтолоба его значение в природе и в жизни человека, его роль в области рыболовства, разведения, различных научных исследований, история исследований и их анализ, а также в нашей стране приведены сведения о преимуществах выращивания тельтолоба интенсивным технологиям.

Ключевые слова: Тельтолобик, фито и зоопланктон, биомелиатор, биоэкологическая особенность.

Abstract. In the article, the biological and ecological characteristics of the silver and bighead carp fish, its importance in nature and in human life, its role in the field of fisheries, breeding, various scientific researches, the history of research and their analysis, as well as the advantages of breeding in aquaculture conditions in our country are discussed. information provided..

Keywords: silver and bighead carp, white and cypress humpback, phyto and zooplankton, biomeliator, bioecological feature.

The shortage of fresh water in the world is increasingly becoming a problem that requires the efficient use of all available water resources, including water bodies of the irrigation system. Especially in the context of complex water use, the issues of development of the fishing network are of concern to the world community. For example, to increase fish productivity, it is very important to artificially form game ichthyofauna in inland waters in such water bodies as the Aral Sea, where fish stocks are very vulnerable and are located in the interior of the continent. Based on this, further improvement of technologies for the use of motley fish in the conditions of pasture aquaculture in order to increase fish productivity is of great scientific and practical importance..

In our republic, based on the needs of the population and market demands, fish farming is growing every year. In this regard, among other things, the Tudakol reservoir, located in the lower reaches of the Zarafshan River, is an extremely important irrigation and large fishery basin, where special attention is paid to large (2 kg and more) promising species typical for pasture aquaculture. breeding of silver carp (*Hypothalmichthys molitrix*) and bigheadcarp (*H. nobilis*). (Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Silver (*Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*) and bighead carp (*Hypophthalmichthys nobilis*)

Bighead and silver carp fishes are representatives of the group of carp fish family (*Cyprinidae*) living in fresh water. Previously, they were divided into the order *Hypophthalmichthys* and *Aristichthys* within the subfamily *Hypophthalmichthyinae*. There are currently three species of this genus and one extinct species. Rivers of Eastern and South-Eastern Asia are considered the homeland of bighead carp fish [1].

Currently, the silver carp (*Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*) and bighead carp (*Hypophthalmichthys nobilis*) species are actively used for two purposes, i.e. cultivation in aquaculture and as a bioremediator. The silver carp feeds on phytoplankton organisms. Most importantly, they use blue-green algae, the metabolic products of which are toxic, including to fish. Silver carp fish prevent biological pollution of water bodies. From an ecological point of view, fast-growing fish occupying the first links of the food chain are suitable objects for extensive and semi-intensive aquaculture. This feature is especially important in the south of the tropical and temperate climate zone [1]. Purely herbivorous fish are not found in the local ichthyofauna of Uzbekistan for objective reasons (as a result of historical geological processes, the Asian mountains, where the bottom of the Tethys Sea has risen, and the Indian plain complex, prevent the passage of herbivorous fish to our territory I did not give) that is why these species are considered promising.

These species were brought twice from the Amur River and from northern China in the early 60s of the last century in order to master the empty environment for phytoplanktonophages in the water bodies of Uzbekistan and to grow fish in polyculture conditions in pond fisheries. They were brought to a newly built pond farm in the Tashkent region, and there, artificial insemination, incubation of eggs, artificial reproduction of larvae and hatchlings were carried out by taking eggs and sperm cells from representatives of both sexes, accelerating the production of sexual products using gonadotropic hormones. Breeding methods have been mastered. From the 1960s to the present day, a large number of generations are regularly collected and distributed to pond farms throughout the region. Also, the white bream is widely distributed in large quantities from pond fishing farms in the water reservoirs of the plain part of the republic for the purpose of obtaining commercial fish and bioremediation. It grows very well in transferred water reservoirs, but in many reservoirs and lakes, the silver carp does not find conditions for natural reproduction.

The adults of the silver carp fish feed only on phytoplankton, which is always found in almost all water bodies in the plains of our republic. Because they feed on phytoplankton, their digestive apparatus and nutrition system have a unique structure. The gills are closely spaced and have transverse septa, and the larynx is lined with a hornlike shell (not enameled as in other carps) that forms a fine web to trap algae cells. With the help of teeth, it forms a bite by wrapping it in a soft mucous shell. A bite of food is transferred to the intestine, the length of the intestine is 10-13 times longer than the length of the body. As food moves through the long intestine, it is well

digested and absorbed. 2 - the daily ration of a young and older silver carp is 70-80% of its body weight, and the feed factor is around 30 units. The share of phytoplankton in the feed can be 90%. It starts feeding on phytoplankton when its body length reaches 3.5 cm. Prefer to diatoms and green algae. It can also eat blue-green algae, making it an important biomeliator in many types of water bodies..

Silver carp is an important catching fish, so this fish has been cultivated in ponds for more than 2,000 years in China. It is also considered an object of fish aquaculture and fishing, it is often used as a biomeliator for cleaning water bodies from algae, including blue-green algae. Currently, it is considered an important object of industrial fishing, aquaculture, as well as world pond fishing in the inland natural water bodies of various countries[4]. (Figure 2).

As a result of anthropogenic influence, in the conditions of eutrophication of water bodies (which is becoming relevant in many countries of the world), more attention has been paid to the use of this fish species as an effective biomeliator. With the help of the filter apparatus in the mouth, the silver carp filters the green and cloudy waters that have "bloomed" and protects the water from the blooms, including pollution with water plants. Because it is a large, fish farming fish, its cleaning efficiency is very high and it is important in various types of water bodies, including avenues, recreation areas, and water bodies for irrigation and energy purposes.

Silver carp fish meat is tasty and fatty. Dietary food can be an important and valuable object. Silver carp fish is the only fish that lives in fresh waters and has fatty substances that reduce cholesterol in the blood, like sea fish. The amount of fat in the meat is 4.5 to 23.5%, the average amount is 8.3-13.1%. The level of fat increases with the increase in body size.

Fig.2.. The size of the world's silver carp fish cultivation (according to UN FAO data)

The main limitation in the use of silver fish is the lack of conditions for its natural reproduction in many water bodies of all countries. This type of pelagophilus requires a sudden increase in water flow over long distances for their natural flight. Fertilized fish eggs swells to the surface of the water and travels up to 100 km with the current [2; 3]. In this way, it is possible to maintain this group of fish by transferring the fry, which are artificially raised in ponds, to the reservoir.

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